

cross invalidation

random walk at the cross roads of neuroimaging, machine learning, brain disorders and informatics.

Why is Python ideal for research software development?

ON JUNE 16, 2019**JUNE 26, 2019** / **BY PRADEEP RAAMANA** /

Python is showing an incredible growth in many fields, including academia. By enumerating the challenges we face in sustainable research software development and how Python's unique strengths are catering to these challenges in this video below, I hope to explain this growth and encourage further adoption of python for research software development!

A closely related blog post focused on my own domain of research is [here \(https://crossinvalidation.com/2018/05/03/lets-focus-our-neuroinformatics-community-efforts-in-python-and-on-software-validation/\)](https://crossinvalidation.com/2018/05/03/lets-focus-our-neuroinformatics-community-efforts-in-python-and-on-software-validation/).

Slides from this talk:

<https://crossinvalidation.files.wordpress.com/2019/06/why-is-python-ideal-for-research-software-dev-raamana-pycon-canada-2018.pdf>) Download

<https://crossinvalidation.files.wordpress.com/2019/06/why-is-python-ideal-for-research-software-dev-raamana-pycon-canada-2018.pdf>)

I'd love to hear your thoughts. [Follow me](#) (<http://twitter.com/raamana>) and let's debate it.

The original talk announcement from pycon Canada 2018 is available [here \(https://2018.pycon.ca/talks/talk-PC-52179\)](https://2018.pycon.ca/talks/talk-PC-52179).

Here is the 10-min talk:

Why is Python ideal for research software ...

One thought on “Why is Python ideal for research software development?”

1. Pingback: [Let's focus our neuroinformatics community efforts in Python and on software validation – cross invalidation \(Edit\)](#)

